

**CONTENTS OF PRESENTATIONS IN STUDYING ENGLISH
LANGUAGE COMPETENCE**

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Abstract: Presentation activity is one of the types of public speaking that is very popular in business and academic environment. Today, it is impossible to imagine a highly qualified manager or engineer who cannot present business or professional information to promote their advertising products or technical ideas, as well as a scientist who does not attend scientific conferences to present research results. a wide range of people. In this regard, training in presentation skills for training specialists in higher educational institutions becomes relevant.

Key words: professional activity, speech communication, foreign language teaching

The presentation of information by students is often formal, because there is no prior training in the art of presenting material in the form of a presentation, which ultimately negatively affects their future career as an engineer, manager, teacher or makes a secret. scientist.

One of the problems of developing presentation skills in academic lyceums is the lack of special subjects for preparing and conducting presentations. This problem can be partially solved by the subject "Foreign language", which is a mandatory component of any course of training and may include teaching presentation skills as one of the types of oral communication.

A number of works are devoted to the structure of the presentation. In general, any presentation can be divided into four main parts: introduction, body,

conclusion, questions and answers. Each part of the presentation has its own characteristics and rules for presenting information.

Many foreign and domestic jobs are devoted to the planning and preparation of presentations and oral reports. Authors focus on developing skills to successfully communicate information by presenting it to audiences at the visual, auditory, verbal, and non-verbal levels. For this purpose, a number of educational and methodological techniques have been developed to successfully plan, prepare and present a presentation.

Planning your presentation is the first and most important step in your work. In order for the presentation to be successful, you need to choose the right topic and reveal it in a complete and interesting way for a specific audience. In order to activate the professionally oriented component of foreign language teaching, it is recommended to choose the topic of the presentation together with the graduate student's supervisor. engaging the audience in the report and helping the speaker to adapt to the audience, thereby setting a successful tone for the presentation.

The first page of the presentation is usually devoted to the title of the lecture, the presentation of the speaker himself and his organization. Choosing the right name for a science project is very important. It should be short and reflect the main idea of the project in order to be understandable to the audience and at the same time interest them from the first minutes of the presentation.

In addition, in the process of forming the name of a scientific presentation in English, you should follow the grammatical and stylistic rules of the scientific style. For example, we use a gerund instead of a noun, we don't use left-defining noun groups and articles. In addition, in English, all words in the names and titles of the presentation, as well as in the names of organizations, are written in capital letters, with the exception of service words.

One of the most common mistakes English learners make is misspelling their first and last names. This should also be taken into account when creating the first page of the presentation. First write the first name, then the last name.

The final presentation of the research project to a wide audience, including representatives of foreign language departments and engineering departments, will use the following evaluation criteria:

- independence of work on the project;
- relevance, importance and completeness of revealing the topic;
- presentation structure and slide design;
- English grammar and style;
- answers to questions;
- scientific and technical terminology;
- artistic and expressive performance, appearance;
- use of visual and technical means.

In order to develop the skills of presentation in a foreign language, the second stage of education - master's degree - was chosen. This stage is an intermediate stage between the initial level of professional knowledge students received at the undergraduate level and the research stage of postgraduate training, which allows undergraduate students to formulate a presentation topic related to their future specialty based on existing knowledge and experiences. or scientific activity.

Foreign language classes are the best way to teach presentation skills, which allows to activate dialogic and monologic speech, as well as to form a number of cognitive and creative abilities of students for the transfer of professional information. In addition, in the process of studying the structure of the presentation and the rules of giving an oral presentation, students develop the skills of successful presentation not only in a foreign language, but also in Russian, which is very important for their further professional activities.

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